

Defining Socially Assistive Robots for the Law: Preliminary results of a systematic review

Marie Schwed-Shenker^[0009-0001-8155-2725], Eduard
Fosch-Villaronga^[0000-0002-8325-5871], and Bart Custers^[0000-0002-3355-8380]

eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies, Leiden University, The Netherlands

Abstract. Over the past two decades, socially assistive (SARs) or interactive (SIRs) robots have been developed rapidly due to their beneficial uses in elderly care, rehabilitation, and education. Given their multiple embodiments and contexts of use, however, defining what these robots are remains a difficult task, which further challenges understanding which legal safeguards developers need to follow to ensure a safe human-robot interaction (HRI). Establishing legislation that adequately frames the issues is complex if these concepts remain confusing. Despite pioneer efforts to characterize what these robots are in international standards and the literature, there is currently no consensus on which legal category they are, and, therefore, related problems are covered unevenly in different pieces of legislation. Following a systematic review, we analyzed 1,359 works (out of 3,446) to clarify definitions, categories, and functionalities of SARs and SIRs to establish a baseline for understanding and regulating these robots. The first results show that the ISO 13482:2014 definition of Mobile Service Robots (MSRs), the formal name for SARs, is incompatible with the current literature. Moreover, more consensus on what qualifies as assistive or interactive under this technology is needed to determine the regulation and safeguards to mitigate the issues these robots entail for users.

Keywords: socially assistive robots · socially interactive robots · social robots · law · personal care · systematic review

1 Introduction

Dictionaries and literature define concepts for people to understand their general meaning, and laws define concepts to frame certain behaviors under the scope of a particular legislation. Framing those definitions is essential for laws to establish roles, rights, and responsibilities for those involved in or impacted by those behaviors, and failing to adhere to them carries not always favorable consequences [35]. A particularly intriguing field is that of *robotics*, which does not enjoy clear definitions in the law (only in standards, which we will expand on later) [36] [50] [15]. On the contrary, the law thinks of ‘products,’ ‘toys,’ ‘medical devices,’ ‘machinery,’ and, recently, ‘artificial intelligence,’ and establishes distinct safeguards for each. That categorization creates confusion among those who are in

the robotics field, who are usually left without clearly knowing what laws they have to follow for their robots and what safeguards they need to apply to ensure a *safe* human-robot interaction [34] and, of course, stay within the legality.

A particularly interesting field without an agreed or legal definition is that of social robots. Since the mid-1990s, after the revolutionary invention of “Cog” and “Kismet” in the MIT AI Lab [33] [5], and for the past two decades, social robots have evolved significantly, adopting new forms, various capabilities and functionalities (such as anthropomorphism). Examples can be found in “NurseBot,” a robot designed to assist older adults in living independently [48], and PEP-PPER, aimed at businesses and schools [21]. Additionally, social robots have been developed for different contexts of use, such as Paro, a zoomorphic therapeutic robot shaped like a seal, intended to reduce stress in patients [46], and QTrobot, a humanoid robot designed to assist non-neurotypical children in school [10].

Given the multitude of shapes, forms, and contexts of use, it is difficult to agree on a standard definition of what constitutes a *social robot*. However, the private sector and academic researchers attempted to solve this definitional labyrinth. Fong et al. [14] conducted an extensive survey, delving into the world of SIRs, announcing those are “. . . robots for which social interaction plays a key role. . . and can be partners, peers, or assistants” (p. 145). A couple of years later, Feil-Seifer and Matarić [13] defined SARs as an intersection between assistive robotics and SIRs, assisting users through social interaction. Of course, SARs using social interactions “. . . may also involve some form of physical contact with users” [4]. At the legal level, laws governing product safety traditionally focused on its physical dimension only [40]. Not having a specific definition led to producers marketing their robots sometimes as toys, sometimes as medical devices, and applying disparity of safeguards to ensure market entrance [57] [61], although not always user safety [16].

Due to the lack of legislative public response to robotics, the private sector had to fill the void [58] [23]. The International Standard Organization (ISO) created ISO 8373:2012 (later revised by ISO 8373:2021) to establish a vocabulary for robots and robotic devices, although *social robots* were not part of it. As technology progressed, and robots started interacting with humans in other contexts rather than industrial or medical, ISO published ISO 13482:2014 for safety requirements for personal care robots, defining *service robots* for the very first time [28]. Under ISO 13482:2014, service robots perform “useful tasks for humans or equipment excluding industrial automation applications.” Personal care robots are categorized as service robots, which “performs actions contributing directly toward improvement in the quality of life of humans, excluding medical applications.” Under personal care robots, *Mobile Servant Robot* is a specific category that can travel, perform tasks, interact with users, handle objects, and exchange information¹. In the new version, and after the name raised many questions, ISO decided to call them *mobile service robots*. Even with these attempts, the lack of clear-cut descriptions regarding social robots remains. The problem is exac-

¹ See ISO 13482:2014(en) Robots and robotic devices - Safety requirements for personal care robots <https://tinyurl.com/4wwe9xea>

erated because this standard shows compliance with the machinery regulation, but not other pieces of legislation such as toys or medical devices².

Given these confusions, the need to determine what these robots and their various functionalities and embodiments are and which safeguards the law deems necessary becomes evident. SARs and SIRs can cause unintentional harm to their users [1]. Privacy and data control are significant in SARs/SIRs stationed in homes and hospitals to assist vulnerable populations. Individuals with cognitive decline may be unable to provide informed consent under Art. 7 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), an EU regulation that protects personal data and ensures individual control. ISO 13482:2014 excludes vulnerable groups (children, elderly persons, pregnant women), even though SARs/SIRs are predominantly developed for them. *Cognitive and emotional protection* are absent in safety standards, but crucial for safe SARs, SIRs, and MSR operation, regardless context of use [9]. ISO 13482:2014 (p. 9) highlights hazard identification in risk assessment (ISO 12100:2010) and, although mentions stress, bypasses cognitive and emotional risks from personal care robots. Similarly, Machinery Regulation 2006/42/EC Annex I 1.2.2 outlines safety measures for machinery but excludes these risks. The General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR) aims to cover unregulated risks and, in Recital 19, references the WHO’s definition of health as physical, mental, and social well-being. However, more guidance in that respect would be needed. Vulnerable groups, noted in Recital 23, are also excluded from ISO 13482:2014.

As scientific knowledge can help inform policies for social robots [7]³, this paper presents the preliminary results of a systematic review identifying the main categories and functionalities of SARs/SIRs. Section 2 presents the systematic review protocol and the search strings used in each search engine. Section 3 presents the preliminary results of 1,359 pieces and the knowledge gathered from this preparatory database and some conclusions and future directions close this article. Section 4 offers conclusion and detailing the next steps for this review.

2 Methods

2.1 Data research and extraction

This systematic review followed the "PRISMA-5" protocol [45] to develop and report systematic review protocols. The protocol was approved by the co-authors to minimize risk of bias. Publications were limited to 2004-2024 as the terms “socially assistive robot”, “socially assistive robots” and “mobile service robots” were not common before 2004. Only English articles were considered, and searches were conducted in IEEE Xplore, PubMed, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, SSRN,

² See Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2023/1586 of 26 July 2023 on harmonized standards for machinery drafted in support of Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023D1586>.

³ See the goals and objectives of the European Research Council (ERC) Starting Grant Safe and Sound at <https://www.laiden.org/projects/erc-stg-safe-sound>.

and Web of Science. Google Scholar was excluded due to algorithm changes [24], and Scopus was inaccessible. Search terms included: “Mobile service robot*”, “Mobile service robots”, “Mobile servant robot*”, “Social* assistive robot*”, “Socially assistive robot”, “Socially assistive robots”, “Socially interactive robot*”, “Socially interactive robot”, “Socially interactive robots”. Initially, 3,446 results were found. Following our inclusion/exclusion criteria, we selected and reviewed 1,359 relevant abstracts⁴.

2.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

This systematic review aimed to create a comprehensive index for defining SAR or SIR using the 12 properties from Fong [14] and Feil-Seifer and Matarić [13]. Well-established categories such as Care and Therapy Robots [6], Mobile Service Robots (ISO 13482:2014), and Companion Robots [31] are also included in this review. Exclusion criteria covered articles on physically assistive or interactive robots, including restraint-type physical assistant robots, restraint-free type physical assistant robots, and person-carrier robots. Exoskeletons, industrial and medical robots, drones, wearable robots, and swarm robots were also excluded.

3 Preliminary results

This section outlines the preliminary outcomes of the systematic review. Key findings for MSR, SAR, and SIR are outlined, followed by discrepancies between academic research and current standards, and socio-ethical considerations.

The initial findings of the search strings were coupled with the 12 properties by Fong [14], Feil-Seifer and Matarić [13], and ISO 13482:2014. The properties chosen are: embodiment, emotion, dialog, personality, human-oriented perception, user modeling, socially situated learning, intentionality [14], user populations, task examples, sophistication of interaction, and role of assistive robot [13]. HRI was added as a property, as it was missing but is still a defining element of SARs/SIRs. The first preliminary finding for *Mobile Service Robot*, is that the current ISO 13482:2014 definition does not include the long-term autonomy of the robot [12] [43] and only defines fully/semi-autonomous options. Well-defined long-term autonomy allows the MSR to develop long-term connection with its user [62]. However, ISO 13482:2014 does not cover long-term safety concerns like emotional attachments. Other remarks on avoiding collision with humans and/or obstacles [22] [32], in dynamic and socially aware navigation [55] [60], or GPS-denied [12] environments, critical for their effective deployment in homes and schools, are poorly addressed in the standard. These environments are characterized by constant changes and unknown human presence, necessitating robust task and path planning [30] [8] and human tracking capabilities to ensure safety and reliability without direct physical contact (as stated in ISO

⁴ The database compiling the literature review can be found following this link <https://tinyurl.com/48s86zs8>

13482:2014). Safety hazards due to collisions do not appear in ISO 13482:2014, which is important to anyone applying or relying on this standard. Further research is necessary to fully mitigate these hazards.

To ensure *safe* and *responsible* HRI and the ethical considerations [1] regarding the privacy and data protection of the user [4] and their confidential medical data, the autonomy of the user vis-à-vis the robot [4], societal acceptance of the robots into our personal spaces are crucial. This review provides a deeper understanding of these aspects, suggesting that safety standards are not enough. ISO 13482:2014 focuses on a narrow understanding of safety, neglecting cognitive and emotional aspects.

ISO 13482:2014 defines MSRs as performing tasks, interacting with users, exchanging information, and handling objects. However, only 3/295 abstracts mentioned information exchange, and just 10 noted HRI. Task performance was mainly studied technically, reflecting the ISO definition. These findings highlight a gap between the ISO 13482:2014 definition and academic research, indicating the need for further research to fully support the standard.

Because MSRs are applicable in diverse contexts, their intricate functionalities may reveal whether certain legislation applies to them or not. The integration of reinforcement learning [30], deep learning [51], and adaptive systems [11] emerges as pivotal in enabling these robots to learn through trial and error. Despite the positive aspects, this method could compromise user safety if, for instance, the robot cooks with peanut oil and then the user suffers from anaphylaxis [56]. More information is needed to understand the scope of these systems pre and post market entrance, as they raise user safety concerns.

Preliminary findings for the search string "*Socially interactive robot**" highlight the importance of refining HRI through user feedback and intuitive controls, with a focus on natural language processing [18] [42] and social cues [49] [38], particularly in elderly care and with non-neurotypical children. ISO 13482:2014 defines interaction with the user as part of MSRs, which is the formal definition for SIRs, yet does not define, source or modify what HRI is⁵. Safety must also apply to the interacting setting which includes both robot and users. Moreover, ethical considerations [27] [54] and cultural factors [39] [38] are crucial for societal and user acceptance, emphasizing the need for ethical and culture-specific designs in autonomous systems.

The thematic area of social awareness underscores the importance of refining interaction quality to enhance HRI dynamics. Non-verbal communication cues such as head/arm/shoulder gestures [2], alongside personalized emotional expressions [44], play a critical role in developing long-lasting bonds with users. Non-verbal cues vary between cultures, contexts, and might be understood differently in different populations. Older people (45 abstracts) and non-neurotypical children (115 abstracts) are the main focus of the research, excluding all other populations. SIR are currently deployed for vulnerable populations, they are meant for everyone. Although these populations are extensively researched, they

⁵ See ISO 8373:2021(en)Robotics - Vocabulary, under "3.15 human-robot interaction", retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/5yzb8f9a>

are excluded from ISO 13482:2014, which shows the discrepancy between the legal framework and academic researchers [17].

Ethical concerns (25 abstracts) on privacy, autonomy, and human-robot relations are pivotal, emphasizing ethical design for societal acceptance across cultures. Topics include machine ethics for autonomous systems [3], ethical issues in child-robot interactions [54], and HRI’s ethical implications [20], underscoring gaps between academic priorities and legal standards. Additionally, emotional expression [37], culturally-influenced tactile stimuli [53], and cultural impacts on HRI [38] highlight the need for culture-specific autonomous systems in social robotics.

The search string “*Social* assistive robot**” showed a significant overlap with the previous search string on SIRs. Both focus mainly on older adult and non-neurotypical children, excluding the general population, and use social and cognitive assistance. Primarily, assisting a user includes physical and social aspects [26], while interacting should only regard exchanging information. The indecisiveness influences the legislation efforts, making it troublesome to know which guidelines need to be followed.

Fundamental design essentials for SARs include ensuring adaptability to different environments [25] [19] [51], user-friendly interfaces for older adults [59] [41], and seamless integration with existing healthcare systems [25] [29]. SARs are meant to integrate into homes and hospitals, their ability to adapt and socialize are crucial for their deployment. Each context of application has different rules and laws, and in each aspect safety must be ensured by further research.

In educational settings, SARs serve as interactive tools to enhance personalized learning experiences and skill development, address ethical challenges associated with technology-mediated education, and ensure broad acceptance among students, teachers, and parents alike. These papers analyze aspects of autistic behavior, such as verbal and non-verbal interactions, gestures, and facial expressions [52], deploy SAR to supervise, assist, encourage, and interact with students [19], and how SAR can cooperate with Special Educators [47] among many others.

4 Conclusion

The evolution of social robots over the past decades has been marked by significant advancements and diversification in their capabilities and applications. Despite these innovations, defining what constitutes SARs/SIRs remains a challenge, as evidenced by various attempts from both academia and standardization bodies like ISO. If this technology is ill-defined, it is highly likely to hinder technological advancements, confuse developers about which safeguards should be followed, and prevent users from being sufficiently safe.

The systematic review presented here aimed to address this challenge by synthesizing recent literature and categorizing SAR/ SIR based on established frameworks and standards. It also highlighted the overlap and distinctions between socially assistive and interactive robots, underscoring the need for clear

definitions. This review is only the initial results, and is currently ongoing. The final product will provide a foundation for further research to refine and expand our understanding of SARs/SIRs for legal purposes.

The findings will contribute to the ERC StG Safe and Sound project, which aims to use scientific knowledge for robotic policy.⁶ The findings from this review will enable us to engage with stakeholders to validate the results and help us prioritize risks. By integrating scientific insights with policy considerations, this work contributes to shaping future directions in the regulation of robotics, ensuring these technologies serve societal needs effectively while upholding legal and ethical standards across diverse cultural contexts.

Acknowledgments. This work has been conducted under the Safe and Sound project, a project that received funding from the European Union’s Horizon-ERC program, Grant Agreement No. 101076929.

References

1. Amodei, D., Olah, C., Steinhardt, J., Christiano, P., Schulman, J., Mané, D.: Concrete problems in ai safety. arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.06565 (2016)
2. Anastasiou, D., Stahl, C., Latour, T.: The role of gesture in social telepresence robots—a scenario of distant collaborative problem-solving. *Social Robots: Technological, Societal and Ethical Aspects of Human-Robot Interaction* pp. 61–83 (2019)
3. Arnold, T., Scheutz, M.: Extended norms: Locating accountable decision-making in contexts of human-robot interaction. *Gruppe. Interaktion. Organisation. Zeitschrift für Angewandte Organisationspsychologie (GIO)* **53**(3), 359–366 (2022)
4. Boada, J.P., Maestre, B.R., Genís, C.T.: The ethical issues of social assistive robotics: A critical literature review. *Technology in Society* **67**, 101726 (2021)
5. Breazeal, D.C.: Kismet - overview (2000), <https://web.media.mit.edu/~cynthiab/research/robots/kismet/overview/overview.html>
6. Broekens, J., Heerink, M., Rosendal, H., et al.: Assistive social robots in elderly care: a review. *Gerontechnology* **8**(2), 94–103 (2009)
7. Calleja, C., Drukarch, H., Fosch-Villaronga, E.: Harnessing robot experimentation to optimize the regulatory framing of emerging robot technologies. *Data & policy* **4**, e20 (2022)
8. Cámara, J., Schmerl, B., Garlan, D.: Software architecture and task plan co-adaptation for mobile service robots. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/ACM 15th International Symposium on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems*. pp. 125–136 (2020)
9. Carpenter, J.: *The Quiet Professional: An investigation of US military Explosive Ordnance Disposal personnel interactions with everyday field robots*. Ph.D. thesis (2013)
10. Costa, A.P., Charpiot, L., Lera, F.R., Ziafati, P., Nazarihorram, A., Van Der Torre, L., Steffgen, G.: More attention and less repetitive and stereotyped behaviors using a robot with children with autism. In: *2018 27th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN)*. pp. 534–539. IEEE (2018)

⁶ See ERC StG Safe and Sound: Towards Evidence-based Policies for Safe and Sound Robots, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101076929>

11. Dayoub, F., Duckett, T.: An adaptive appearance-based map for long-term topological localization of mobile robots. In: 2008 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems. pp. 3364–3369. IEEE (2008)
12. Deshmukh, R.A., Hasamnis, M.A.: A navigation scheme for autonomous mobile service robots working in gps denied commercial indoor spaces. In: 2023 International Conference on Communication, Circuits, and Systems (IC3S). pp. 1–5. IEEE (2023)
13. Feil-Seifer, D., Mataric, M.J.: Defining socially assistive robotics. In: 9th International Conference on Rehabilitation Robotics, 2005. ICORR 2005. pp. 465–468. IEEE (2005)
14. Fong, T., Nourbakhsh, I., Dautenhahn, K.: A survey of socially interactive robots. *Robotics and autonomous systems* **42**(3-4), 143–166 (2003)
15. Fosch-Villaronga, E., Drukarch, H.: AI for healthcare robotics. CRC Press (2022)
16. Fosch-Villaronga, E., Drukarch, H.: Accounting for diversity in robot design, testbeds, and safety standardization. *International Journal of Social Robotics* **15**(11), 1871–1889 (2023)
17. Fosch-Villaronga, E., Van der Hof, S., Lutz, C., Tamò-Larrieux, A.: Toy story or children story? putting children and their rights at the forefront of the artificial intelligence revolution. *AI & society* **38**(1), 133–152 (2023)
18. Foster, M.E.: Natural language generation for social robotics: opportunities and challenges. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* **374**(1771), 20180027 (2019)
19. Gouraguine, S., Salhi, I., Qbadou, M., Mansouri, K.: Learner personality type effect on attitude toward social assistive robotics in learning for children with disabilities. In: 2022 2nd International Conference on Innovative Research in Applied Science, Engineering and Technology (IRASET). pp. 1–5. IEEE (2022)
20. de Graaf, M.M.: An ethical evaluation of human–robot relationships. *International journal of social robotics* **8**, 589–598 (2016)
21. Group, U.R.: Pepper the humanoid and programmable robot (2022), <https://www.aldebaran.com/en/pepper>
22. Grundmann, T., Eidenberger, R., Zoellner, R.D., Xue, Z., Ruehl, S., Zoellner, J.M., Dillmann, R., Kuehnle, J., Verl, A.: Integration of 6d object localization and obstacle detection for collision free robotic manipulation. In: 2008 IEEE/SICE International Symposium on System Integration. pp. 66–71. IEEE (2008)
23. Guihot, M., Matthew, A.F., Suzor, N.P.: Nudging robots: Innovative solutions to regulate artificial intelligence. *Vand. J. Ent. & Tech. L.* **20**, 385 (2017)
24. Gusenbauer, M., Haddaway, N.R.: Which academic search systems are suitable for systematic reviews or meta-analyses? evaluating retrieval qualities of google scholar, pubmed, and 26 other resources. *Research synthesis methods* **11**(2), 181–217 (2020)
25. Hasenauer, R., Belviso, C., Ehrenmueller, I.: New efficiency: Introducing social assistive robots in social eldercare organizations. In: 2019 IEEE International Symposium on Innovation and Entrepreneurship (TEMS-ISIE). pp. 1–6. IEEE (2019)
26. HousingCare: Care support for older people (2020), <https://housingcare.org/care-advice/>
27. Howard, A.: Are we trusting ai too much? examining human-robot interactions in the real world. In: Proceedings of the 2020 ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction. pp. 1–1 (2020)
28. Jacobs, T., Virk, G.S.: Iso 13482-the new safety standard for personal care robots. In: ISR/Robotik 2014; 41st International Symposium on Robotics. pp. 1–6. VDE (2014)

29. Jayawardena, C., Kuo, I.H., Broadbent, E., MacDonald, B.A.: Socially assistive robot healthbot: Design, implementation, and field trials. *IEEE Systems Journal* **10**(3), 1056–1067 (2014)
30. Jiang, Y., Yang, F., Zhang, S., Stone, P.: Task-motion planning with reinforcement learning for adaptable mobile service robots. In: 2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS). pp. 7529–7534. IEEE (2019)
31. Kachouie, R., Sedighadeli, S., Khosla, R., Chu, M.T.: Socially assistive robots in elderly care: a mixed-method systematic literature review. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* **30**(5), 369–393 (2014)
32. Kuehnle, J., Verl, A., Xue, Z., Ruehl, S., Zoellner, J.M., Dillmann, R., Grundmann, T., Eidenberger, R., Zoellner, R.D.: 6d object localization and obstacle detection for collision-free manipulation with a mobile service robot. In: 2009 International Conference on Advanced Robotics. pp. 1–6. IEEE (2009)
33. Laboratory, T.C.S.M.A.I.: Cog: A history in pictures, http://www.ai.mit.edu/projects/cog/history_of_cog.htm
34. Lasota, P.A., Fong, T., Shah, J.A., et al.: A survey of methods for safe human-robot interaction. *Foundations and Trends® in Robotics* **5**(4), 261–349 (2017)
35. Leenes, R.: Framing techno-regulation: An exploration of state and non-state regulation by technology. *Legisprudence* **5**(2), 143–169 (2011)
36. Leenes, R., Lucivero, F.: Laws on robots, laws by robots, laws in robots: Regulating robot behaviour by design. *Law, Innovation and Technology* **6**(2), 193–220 (2014)
37. Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk, B., Wilson, P.A.: Compassion, empathy and sympathy expression features in affective robotics. In: 2016 7th IEEE international conference on cognitive infocommunications (CogInfoCom). pp. 000065–000070. IEEE (2016)
38. Lim, V., Rooksby, M., Cross, E.S.: Social robots on a global stage: establishing a role for culture during human–robot interaction. *International Journal of Social Robotics* **13**(6), 1307–1333 (2021)
39. Mansouri, M., Taylor, H.: Does cultural robotics need culture? conceptual fragmentation and the problems of merging culture with robot design. *International Journal of Social Robotics* **16**(2), 385–401 (2024)
40. Martinetti, A., Chemweno, P.K., Nizamis, K., Fosch-Villaronga, E.: Redefining safety in light of human-robot interaction: A critical review of current standards and regulations. *Frontiers in chemical engineering* **3**, 666237 (2021)
41. Mayer, P., Beck, C., Panek, P.: Examples of multimodal user interfaces for socially assistive robots in ambient assisted living environments. In: 2012 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Cognitive Infocommunications (CogInfoCom). pp. 401–406. IEEE (2012)
42. Mazzei, D., Chiarello, F., Fantoni, G.: Analyzing social robotics research with natural language processing techniques. *Cognitive Computation* **13**(2), 308–321 (2021)
43. Mudrova, L., Lacerda, B., Hawes, N.: An integrated control framework for long-term autonomy in mobile service robots. In: 2015 European Conference on Mobile Robots (ECMR). pp. 1–6. IEEE (2015)
44. Murray, J.C., Cañamero, L., Bard, K.A., Ross, M.D., Thorsteinsson, K.: The influence of social interaction on the perception of emotional expression: a case study with a robot head. In: *Advances in Robotics: FIRA RoboWorld Congress 2009, Incheon, Korea, August 16-20, 2009. Proceedings 12*. pp. 63–72. Springer (2009)
45. Page, M.J., McKenzie, J.E., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J.M., Akl, E.A., Brennan, S.E., et al.: The prisma 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *bmj* **372** (2021)
46. PARO Robots U.S., I.: Paro therapeutic robot (2014), <https://www.parorobots.com/>

47. Paul, N., Ramesh, S., Bhattacharya, C., Ramesh, J., Vijayan, P.: Can non-humanoid social robots reduce workload of special educators: An online and in-premises field study. In: 2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA). pp. 11386–11392. IEEE (2021)
48. Project, T.I.: Nursebot - personal mobile robotic assistants for the elderly (2005), <https://theindexproject.org/post/nursebot>
49. Ravindra, P., De Silva, S., Matsumoto, T., Lambacher, S.G., Higashi, M.: Development of a social learning mechanism for a humanoid robot. In: 2008 International Conference on Intelligent Sensors, Sensor Networks and Information Processing. pp. 243–248. IEEE (2008)
50. Richards, N.M., Smart, W.D.: How should the law think about robots? In: Robot law, pp. 3–22. Edward Elgar Publishing (2016)
51. Robinson, F., Nejat, G.: A deep learning human activity recognition framework for socially assistive robots to support reablement of older adults. In: 2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA). pp. 6160–6167. IEEE (2023)
52. Salhi, I., Gouraguine, S., Qbadou, M., Mansouri, K.: A socially assistive robot therapy for pedagogical rehabilitation of autistic learners. In: 2022 2nd International Conference on Innovative Research in Applied Science, Engineering and Technology (IRASET). pp. 1–4. IEEE (2022)
53. Silvera-Tawil, D., Rye, D., Velonaki, M.: Artificial skin and tactile sensing for socially interactive robots: A review. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **63**, 230–243 (2015)
54. Tolksdorf, N.F., Siebert, S., Zorn, I., Horwath, I., Rohlfing, K.J.: Ethical considerations of applying robots in kindergarten settings: Towards an approach from a macroperspective. *International Journal of Social Robotics* **13**, 129–140 (2021)
55. Truong, X.T., Ngo, T.D.: Toward socially aware robot navigation in dynamic and crowded environments: A proactive social motion model. *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering* **14**(4), 1743–1760 (2017)
56. Villaronga, E.F., Albo-Canals, J.: Implications of the google’s us 8,996,429 b1 patent in cloud robotics-based therapeutic researches. In: Service Robots. IntechOpen (2017)
57. Villaronga, E.F., Virk, G.S.: Legal issues for mobile servant robots. In: Advances in Robot Design and Intelligent Control: Proceedings of the 25th Conference on Robotics in Alpe-Adria-Danube Region (RAAD16). pp. 605–612. Springer (2017)
58. Villaronga, E.F., et al.: Robots, standards and the law: Rivalries between private standards and public policymaking for robot governance. *Computer Law & Security Review* **35**(2), 129–144 (2019)
59. Werner, K., Oberzaucher, J., Werner, F.: Evaluation of human robot interaction factors of a socially assistive robot together with older people. In: 2012 sixth International Conference on complex, intelligent, and software intensive systems. pp. 455–460. IEEE (2012)
60. Weser, M., Off, D., Zhang, J.: Htn robot planning in partially observable dynamic environments. In: 2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. pp. 1505–1510. IEEE (2010)
61. Winfield, A.F., van Maris, A., Winkle, K., Jirotko, M., Salvini, P., Webb, H., Scott, A.S., Freeman, J.L., Kunze, L., Slovak, P., et al.: Ethical risk assessment for social robots: case studies in smart robot toys. In: Towards Trustworthy Artificial Intelligent Systems, pp. 61–76. Springer (2022)
62. Yang, W., Xie, Y.: Can robots elicit empathy? the effects of social robots’ appearance on emotional contagion. *Computers in Human Behavior: Artificial Humans* **2**(1), 100049 (2024)